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VALUE ASPECTS OF VOCATIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

The article considers the problems of vocational training of preschool teacher in the system of preschool education. Features of the modern preschool children and the changed position of an adult in relation to a child have been considered.

Attention is drawn to the fact that the university shall ensure conditions for the formation of professional values, which are important for the future preschool specialists, valuable for the work of a preschool teacher, a presentation about the essence of teaching activities in general and the specifics of their implementation in the preschool. The main directions of improving the professional training of the future preschool teachers in modern conditions have been indicated.

The understanding of the education values and goals has been justified to be the basis for the training of preschool teachers, based on the ideas of morality, democracy, humanism and civil responsibility, which is expressed in the requirements for the preschool teacher personality and professionalism.

Keywords: *vocational education, preschool education, professional training of personnel, methodological bases for teacher training, the value of education.*

Апрелева І. В. Ціннісні аспекти професійної підготовки майбутніх спеціалістів дошкільної освіти. *В статті розглядаються проблеми професійної підготовки вихователів у системі дошкільної освіти. Проаналізовано особливості сучасних дітей дошкільного віку і позицію дорослого по відношенню до дитини, що змінилася .*

Звертається увага на те, що у закладах вищої освіти необхідно забезпечити створення умов, що сприятимуть формуванню у майбутніх спеціалістів дошкільної освіти професійних цінностей, важливих для роботи вихователем, уявлення про суть педагогічної діяльності в цілому та специфіки її втілення в дошкільній сфері. Визначені основні напрями удосконалення професійної підготовки майбутнього педагога в сучасних умовах.

Обґрунтовано, що розуміння цінностей і цілей освіти є основою підготовки педагогів дошкільної освіти, що базується на ідеях моралі, демократії, гуманізму та громадянської відповідальності, що виражається у вимогах до особистості та професійності вихователя.

Ключові слова: *професійна освіта, дошкільна освіта, професійна*

підготовка кадрів, методологічні основи підготовки педагогів, цінності освіти.

Апрелева И. В. *Ценностные аспекты профессиональной подготовки будущих специалистов дошкольного образования. В статье рассматриваются проблемы профессиональной подготовки воспитателей в системе дошкольного образования. Рассмотрены особенности современных детей дошкольного возраста и изменившаяся позиция взрослого по отношению к ребёнку.*

Обращается внимание на то, что в вузе необходимо обеспечить создание условий, способствующих формированию у будущих специалистов дошкольного образования профессиональных ценностей, значимых для работы воспитателем, представления о сути педагогической деятельности в целом и специфике ее воплощения в дошкольной сфере. Обозначены основные направления совершенствования профессиональной подготовки будущего педагога в современных условиях.

Обосновано, что понимание ценностей и целей образования составляют основу подготовки педагогов дошкольного образования, базирующейся на идеях нравственности, демократии, гуманизма и гражданской ответственности, что выражается в требованиях к личности и профессионализму воспитателя.

Ключевые слова: *профессиональное образование, дошкольное образование, профессиональная подготовка кадров, методологические основы подготовки педагогов, ценности образования.*

Target setting. In modern Ukraine, the education system is continuously developing; it is characterized by constant renewal and self-development. The analysis of normative and legal acts affecting the reform and development of the educational system allows concluding them being addressed to the individual and the professionalism of the educational process subjects.

In recent years, the interest of researchers in problems of the formation of a creative personality, capable of manifesting and regulating the vital activity based on essential value orientations, has become more acute in higher education. For several years, the range of tasks aimed at improvement of preschool education. An orientation toward the formation of specialists ready for self-education, self-determination, having the cognitive, organizational, communicative, creative, and

other abilities, remain the most important indicator of the modern vocational education.

Universities shall train the preschool specialists considering the uniqueness of the preschool period and the tasks of the domestic education system. This article addresses the value aspects of training of highly skilled preschool specialists. The value approach has a great educational potential, as directed to the formation of a basis of personal culture, mentality and professional position of the future teacher, who expresses the cumulative attitude of a specialist to various aspects of the professional activity.

Analysis of recent researches and publications. The issues of professional and pedagogical training of specialists in preschool education are revealed in the works of A. Bogush, N. Gavrish, E. Krutij, N. Lysenko, L. Pokroevoj, T. Tan'ko, A. Chagovec, T. Shvecand others. A number of publications of domestic researchers vividly illustrates that the training of a preschool teacher, first, must meet the present requirements, because this is the first educational link on which the level of education and upbringing of the future generation depends. Many scientists point to the need for a renewal of education on the value basis.

The works of such psychology specialists as B. Anan'ev, I. Beh, L. Vygotsky, V. Davydov, S. Rubinshtejn, D. Uznadze and such pedagogy specialists as A. Aleksjuk, V. Lugovoj, A. Savchenko, A. Suhomlinskaja and others study the educational values and individual orientation.

The formation of valuable professional orientations in the training of future teachers is an issue, studied by T. Bobro, L. Vedernikova, O. Grinjova, V. Denisenko, G. Koval'chuk, E. Otich, G. Pecherskaja and others. The most researchers agree with the opinion that value professional orientation is the most important component of the teacher personality structure, which determines the creative behavior and attitude to a child as the highest pedagogical value.

Article objective statement. The objective of the articles to analyze the important professional quality of teachers, to consider the value priorities for

professional orientation of students rial of the research. The basic task of modern preschool educationis equipping a child not with a system of branch knowledge as much as with the science of life.

The present society imposes high requirements to preschool teachers, based on which they plot an educational process so that not only the children capabilities and abilities are considered, but the maximum development of their personality is realized. Working with preschoolers requires maturity and flexibility, creativity and great patience of adult persons. Everyday, the teachers have to solve diverse and complex professional tasks, master and fulfill new functions demanded by modern society.

I. Zimmjaja says that it is the professional and psychological portrait of a preschool specialist that is characterized by «the most developed professionally subjective, personal (individual psychological) characteristics and communicative (interactive) qualities in their totality in comparison with the teacher of any other level and form of education» [1, p. 159].

G. Kovalchuk considers that important step of professional skills simulation of future specialists' professional is «formation of positive professional value orientations that allow building the ideal model of the future professional activity in consciousness of the student, which serves as a bench mark in professional self-development» [2, p. 17].

The personal orientation of the teacher plays an important role in his work. It is reflected in the professionogram and characterized the social, moral, vocational - pedagogical and educational orientation of the teacher.

The indicator of the professional competence of the teacher is not only special knowledge, knowledge of information, mastered technologies of teaching and upbringing, but also a general and pedagogical culture that provides personal development, going beyond the normative activities, the ability to create and transmit values.

It is important for modern practitioners to understand that preschool education is not at all a set of educational technologies or methodical methods. This is a kind of system of developmental education, focused on the principles of development of children's activities, the use of which will provide a personal oriented approach in the education and upbringing of preschool children.

According to I. Beh, «the philosophy of personality-oriented education provides the child with the right to freedom of choice of a value position, the value of the human spirit and the value of life in general, the possibility of its effective implementation when he has position for over coming disharmony in experience, behavior, communication, and activity» [3] .

The work of the teacher is connected with the processes of inner being of a child who need more recognition, support, understanding and assistance than in hard technologies. Important is the teacher's ability to understand the problem and on to motivate pupils the use in the game of new knowledge, ways of solving game problems that would help them to enter into a relationship interacting with each other, open up a new game space. According to P. Lesgaft, the classical author of domestic preschool pedagogic, a teacher in such a situation should «to lead the child to the thinking, arouse passion, intellectual and strong-willed activity, to accustom him to manage and manage oneself» [4, p.113].

Modern children are psychologically different: they live in a different intellectual environment development, increase in the volume, processing time and storage of information, high rationalization, stereotypization and algorithmization of activities, the dominance of information technology and virtuality of the environment.

This gives grounds to consider the media-developing environment as a space for the life of a modern child, where the media is an important factor in its socialization [5].

Television becomes the most influential, when a child has limited communication with parents and other socialization agents and is limited in alternative values broadcast on television, attitudes and beliefs.

Unfortunately, most researchers (V. Zasluzhenyuk, V. Semichenko, N. Sinyagina, R. Ovcharova, etc.) agree that modern parents «are rend from their own children», they read less to them, are less interested in their problems, offer easier and entertaining activities. As a result, children perceive the environment through a TV screen or monitor, often in a distorted and reworked form.

The life space of a modern child was filled with entertainment programs, and often advertising; they dominate and compete with the book. All this leads to a reluctance to learn additional information, to the superficiality in its perception, the inability to concentrate attention, to independently comprehend the new, to the predominance of the visual form of remembering the material, to the stereotyped thinking processes, etc. As a result, not only the structure of mental activity of children is substantially transformed, but also the personality sphere, which leads to a decrease in the motivation of achievements, the predominance of the ego - centrality, inability to take into account the opinions and interests of others, etc.

Due to these circumstances, and also taking into account the social significance, complexity and originality of child development, it is necessary to focus on a qualitative change in the content of the training process for teachers of preschool education institutions (PEI), which should not be reduced only to a broad and widespread mastery of competences. Students need knowledge about the nature and character of sociocultural transformations in the structure of childhood itself.

The leading role of the teacher as organizer and moderator of the educational process in preschool education institutions is aimed at the organization of an individualized developing environment, emotionally comfortable for every child and adult. First of all in the notion of «developing environment» we include intersubjective interaction of teachers and children.

The child and the teacher are subjects of one educational space, and the position, on the one hand, of duality and separation and, on the other, openness and interpenetration of the world of the teacher and the child are defined in preschool education as the most important way of organizing the pedagogical environment of the mutual influence of teachers and children.

The importance of partnership relations between the teacher and the child, the democratic style of communication between the adult and the child is determined in the studies of E. Arkin, L. Vygotskyi, A. Leontiev, V. Sukhomlinskyi, T. Ponimanskaya, and others.

The problems of the teacher's relationship with children on the basis of the principles of humanism and the creative approach to the formation of personality are solved by contemporaries, Sh. Amonashvili, I. Beh, O. Kononko, N. Skripnik and others.

T. Ponimanskaya notes «the mastery of the teacher is precisely the ability to appeal to the feelings and experience of children expediently and correctly, to tactfully and delicately discuss with them issues that excite, unobtrusively and accurately help in the value development of the world of people» [6, p. 3].

Unfortunately, there are few teachers who are able to accept the aspiration of children to authorship, who are ready to build the educational process as an interaction of equal partners. Against this background, the importance of subject-subject interactions increases due to which the child grows up, acquires spiritual aspirations and values, which is a necessary basis for personal self-construction in the future.

The full development of the personality does not happen by itself, it presupposes a purposefully carried out action the teacher on the child, which does not contradict the humanistic orientation of the pedagogical process and is aimed at the implementation and compliance with certain rules and regulations. Thus the pupil is attached to the socio-cultural experience, values, traditions and prohibitions.

According to T. Pirozhenko, the teacher-humanist must have kindness, sincerity, devotion and boundless faith in the child. «Only in this way we can expect an open child's heart for peace, harmonious relations with relatives, a sense of security, confidence, which motivates the child to independently choose socially meaningful values in solving his problems. It is such a humane system of the child's relationships that leads him along the path to self-perfection» [7].

It is obvious that before educating a self-sufficient person in children who is free in his thoughts and manifestations, the teacher must himself reflect on his own ability to free thinking, delight and joy from other people's successes, the desire to do good and to feel the beauty of the world around him.

V. Kovalchuk defines the following necessary conditions for a professional self-development in the process of preparing the future specialist:

- orientation of the learning process on the formation of purposefulness of the future specialist on self-actualization and self-determination in the future professional activity;

- enriching the content of learning with a system of notions and concepts, orient future specialists to reflection, self-projecting, self-learning, self-organization, self-development in the sphere of professionally significant personal qualities [2, p.14].

It should be pointed out, that recently in pedagogical education there has been an increase in interest in reflection, reflexive psychology, existential psychology, phenomenology in the study of the professional position of the teacher [8]. However, there is some caution in studying these areas, and the inadequacy of the use of knowledge in practice.

We assume that the success of the professional training of future teachers of preschool education will depend on the direction of the educational process to build their leadership qualities. The peculiarities of such training include: the formation of values (human, spiritual, and practical) for students, respectful

attitude to the child's personality, self-development and self-realization in the future professional activity.

Representations about the values and goals of education form the foundation training for teachers of preschool teachers based on the ideas of morality, democracy, humanism and civic responsibility, which is expressed in the requirements for the personality and professionalism of the teacher of preschool education.

The value foundations of the professional activity of the teacher of preschool education are the base on which his intellect develops and the pedagogical technology is built. Its main values include: human (the child as the main pedagogical value and the teacher, capable of self-development, cooperation with him, social protection of his personality, help and support of his personality, creativity); spiritual (the total pedagogical experience of mankind, reflected in pedagogical theories and ways of pedagogical thinking, aimed at the formation of a non-standard personality); practical (methods of practical pedagogical activity, tested by the practice of the educational system, interactive pedagogical technologies that ensure the active inclusion of trainees in various activities); personal pedagogical abilities, individual characteristics of the teacher as a subject of pedagogical culture, the pedagogical process and his own life-creation, contributing to the creation of personal-humane interaction .

In a period of rapid transition to new socio-cultural relations in the preschool environment, high-level professionals are needed that can adequately assess the current requirements for the child's personality and implement the corresponding educational process in the PEI. Therefore, if we talk about higher professional education, its main tasks are focused not only on acquiring the necessary knowledge by future specialists (because knowledge alone does not at times provide the ability to act effectively), but also on the understanding of the value of the changes in that area, where they have to work. And this requires the presence of reflexive activity and practical work on filling the special professional

skills «lively content». Understanding differs from knowledge by a higher degree of meaning fullness, since it allows one to develop an attitude toward one's own knowledge and to produce a reflection on them. Understanding is based on a dialogue reflecting at least two different positions, which sets the space for reflection both of one's own activity and the activities of other people.

Therefore, the maxim «From knowledge to understanding the child» should be the generally recognized slogan of the vocational training system for preschool workers.

Conclusions from this study and prospects for further research. In such a manner, the professional values of future teachers of preschool education are formed in the process of updating such axiological components as understanding and acceptance of the essence of the pedagogical profession, the specifics of its implementation at the preschool level of education, awareness of the reached level of professional competence as a teacher of preschool education, and the need for further self-development.

The process of professional training of future teachers of preschool education requires a rethinking in the context of taking into account the characteristics of modern childhood. We are talking about a revision of the methodological foundations of the process of training personnel for the PEI system, the dominance of personality-oriented, reflexive, contextual, synergetic, phenomenological, hermeneutic, existential and other approaches in vocational education as key in determining the ambiguous pedagogical positions of preschool theory and practice.

The meaning of vocational training is seen in teaching students interaction with preschool children in the course of joint activities based on mutual understanding and personal communication, emotional and spiritual unity. This will ensure the anticipatory nature of vocational education, the high quality of training teachers, ready to implement humanely programs of a new generation in the preschool educational.

Further research is aimed at examining modern methodological approaches to the formation of the vocational value orientation of future pedagogical staff in pre-school education.

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